

Intellectual
Property
Office

Certificate of Registration for a UK Design

Design number: 6429645

Grant date: 17 March 2025

Registration date: 11 March 2025

This is to certify that,

in pursuance of and subject to the provision of Registered Designs Act 1949, the design of which a representation or specimen is attached, had been registered as of the date of registration shown above in the name of

Dr.Salim Sharieff, Dr. Nadeem Pasha Kaleem, Dr. Jaksankumar Dahyabhai

Patel, Dr.Somarouthu Venkata Govardhana Veera Anjaneya Prasad, Dr.

Sanjeev Kumar Shrivastava, Dr. Pamarthi Venkata Sivarambabu, Dr.Suvetha

Poyyamani Sunddararaj, Dr.Alok Kumar Srivastava, Dr. Biswajit Patra, Dr.

Appurva Jain

in respect of the application of such design to:

Solar Powered Agricultural Vehicle

International Design Classification:

Version: 15-2025

Class: 15 MACHINES, NOT ELSEWHERE SPECIFIED

Subclass: 03 AGRICULTURAL AND FORESTRY MACHINERY

Adam Williams

Comptroller-General of Patents, Designs and Trade Marks

Intellectual Property Office

The attention of the Proprietor(s) is drawn to the important notes overleaf.

Representation of Designs

